

Impact indicators and solutions for improving the energy efficiency of buildings

Erdashev Tayir Farxad uli

Karakalpak State University named after Berdak. 3rd year student of the Faculty of Civil Engineering

Scientific supervisor: **Torebek Uzakov**

Abstract: The building system is analyzed taking into account increasing the energy efficiency of buildings and international experience. Today, the general condition of buildings under construction is created in accordance with international experience. The article describes impact indicators and solutions for improving the energy efficiency of buildings.

Key words: Construction, economics, energy, reform, solution, discomfort, energy consumption, insulation.

The majority of existing residential buildings in the Republic of Uzbekistan are houses designed and built according to individual individual projects. When constructing such houses, the climate of Central Asia, including Tashkent, is considered hot and sharply continental. In the premises of a building operated in such climatic conditions, the temperature in summer is 40-45^oC, and the room temperature exceeds 45^oC. This situation creates an uncomfortable microclimate in the room. Analysis of residential buildings being built in the climatic conditions of Uzbekistan from the point of view of increasing energy efficiency, analysis of projects of modern residential buildings under construction in terms of energy-efficient roofs, door windows, as well as the location of the residential building in

the region. It is very important to take into account the hot and dry climate of Uzbekistan.

An energy efficient house is a building that consumes very little energy to maintain a comfortable microclimate inside the building. Energy savings in such buildings reach up to 90%. Annual energy consumption in buildings of this type can be less than 15 kWh per 1 m². For example, the majority of private houses being built today (reinforced concrete foundation, “warm floor” system without additional heating, walls 1.5 brick thick with cement plaster, standard plastic windows, roof insulation 150 mm and without supply and exhaust installation in the ventilation system) amount of energy used for heating is 110-130 kWh per year per 1 m². The following classification of houses has been adopted in the European Union.

1. Low Energy Homes: Homes that consume at least 50% less energy than conventional buildings and meet current energy standards.

2. Ultra Low Energy Homes: 70-90% energy efficient compared to conventional homes. Examples include the German Passive House, the French Effinergie and the Swiss Minergie, which clearly define the requirements for ultra-low energy houses. Many foreign countries are implementing a number of administrative and economic regulatory and support measures aimed at improving the energy efficiency of buildings.

1. Introduction of energy saving standards, strict building codes, indicators within the framework, indicators related to limiting energy consumption for heating and lighting of the building. Improving the energy efficiency of residential buildings includes the following measures: building standards for new buildings, construction of passive energy and virtually energy-free buildings, retrofitting existing buildings from an energy efficiency point of view, and introducing building certification. According to final statistics from the International Energy Agency, in 19 of its member countries, the above-mentioned

energy efficiency policies have played a decisive role, according to which the figure has been 1.3% since 1990. Today, the current trend in residential construction is the construction of “green buildings”. As part of this trend, unified standards have not been developed in the world, therefore, in international experience, an approach to determining the environmental level of a building has not been developed. Proprietary standards are only available in the UK, France, Germany, Italy, Australia, Japan and China. In the United States, there are four standards for green buildings. Some states provide subsidies to owners of Green Building Council certified buildings.

Many states update building codes annually with the goal of cutting the energy consumption of all new buildings in half by 2030. A number of cities have legally established energy efficiency ratings for buildings under the ENERGY STAR program, which includes tables from 1 to 100 and above and is suitable for buildings with an area of more than 1000 square meters.

2. Providing government support and subsidies to improve the energy efficiency of the building. In the UK, the Warm Front program targets low-income households by insulating and improving the energy efficiency of their heating systems, with an investment of £50 million. This program is also valid in the USA. In Japan, subsidies are provided by the New Energy and Industrial Technology Development Organization (NEDO), which renovates residential buildings in accordance with thermal insulation (based on the Energy Efficiency Law), installs energy-efficient household appliances using renewable energy sources, and equips with efficient systems. As a result of the subsidies, new homes are 15% more energy efficient and retrofitted homes require 25% less energy than when they were built. Owners of new and renovated homes must report increases in energy consumption to NEDO every three years. The level of basic energy demand in new modern buildings being built in Poland, the following technology is useful for different building energy per

kW/m²: - most buildings with 20-30 cm concrete walls and highly effective individual mineral wool insulation of only 20-25 cm, heated by central heating systems. It is advisable to cover polystyrene with thermal insulation material at least 20 cm in places or 15 cm on a flat roof with one layer of wooden roofing on the slopes. In individual houses, mineral wool insulation is 20-25 cm, in houses with individual gas boilers the wall thickness is 20-30 cm, in walls made of hollow bricks the insulation thickness is 15 cm. The volume of increased thermal insulation of walls, ceilings and foundations corresponds to high thermal standards, thickness is about 15 cm. Testing the effectiveness of building ventilation systems through the use of modern insulated windows and doors to prevent mold and rot on walls and walls. ceilings due to insufficient ventilation allow. The construction of energy-efficient buildings in different parts of the world began after the global energy crisis of 1974. At the same time, the first energy-efficient high-rise building project began to be built earlier, in 1972, in Manchester, America. The building has seven floors and a two-level garage. Energy costs for ventilation (ventilation) of the building are compensated by reducing the intake of outside air. This is achieved through the use of a rational planning solution. The project also uses heat recuperators, which reduce energy consumption for air cooling and heating by 60-75%. By changing the level of natural light, adjusting the light intensity and the artificial lighting control system, it allows you to save energy. Photovoltaic solar panels installed on the west and east facades also “produce” energy for the building. They are also located at the top of the building.

The total area of solar panels is more than 1,500 square meters per façade. The total power of photovoltaic panels is about 300,000 kW. The refrigerant circulation channels partially provide optimal cooling (permeate the building). “Partially” - since the windows in the southern part of the building contribute to cooling - they are double-glazed and have inter-pane ventilation. In addition, the windows are

equipped with blinds; the position of their slats changes automatically depending on the movement of the Sun across the sky. And to top it all off, solar heating of the building reduces the cost of individual building materials.

In conclusion, enough experiments and tests in the field of energy efficiency have been carried out in the world, and they need to be considered in accordance with the climatic conditions of our Central Asia. Suggestions and decisions of Uzbek scientists should be taken into account when implementing the above measures. Based on world experience, it is necessary to study their achievements and shortcomings and adapt them to our conditions. Of course, taking into account all the above points, it is necessary to comply with the requirements of the QMS and regulatory documents.

References:

1. Toshpulatov S. U., Umarov Sh. A. (2021). INSTRUMENTAL-EDUCATIONAL-DYNAMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL AND CONSTRUCTIVE SOLUTIONS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL # 2 FERGANI. ONLINE SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT ANALYSIS, 1 (6), 10-15.
2. Yuvmitov A.S., Tashpolatov S.U., Oktamov B.B. (2021). An instrumental study of the dynamic characteristics of secondary schools with different curriculum and building solutions in Fergana. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND APPLIED SCIENCES, 2(11), 200-208.
3. Yuvmitov A.S., Toshpo'Latov S.U.U. (2021). DYNAMICS OF COMMON EDUCATION SCHOOLS BUILDINGS LOCATED IN THE CITY OF FERGANA WITH DIFFERENT SIZES AND DESIGN SOLUTIONS

4. INSTRUMENTAL STUDY OF CHARACTERISTICS. Scientific Progress, 2(6), 1283–1290.
5. Sagdiev K.S., Yuvmitov A.S., Kadirov G.M. (2020). Assessment of the seismic resistance of existing preschool educational institutions and recommendations for ensuring their seismic safety. American Journal of Applied Science, 2(12), 90–99.
6. Shukurov I. S., Sagatov B. O', and Niyatkul, G'. (2022). Alternative solutions for using local materials to improve the energy efficiency of the roof structure. Science and Education, 3(4), 548-554.
7. Asatov N. A., Shukurov I. S., Sagatov B. Yu., Usmonova M. O. (2022). Calculation of heat loss from building floors. Science and Education, 3(4), 390–395.
8. Sagatov B. U. (2022). The state of construction of energy efficient buildings in Uzbekistan. Science and Education, 3(1), 261-265.
9. Asatov N. A., Sagatov B. U., Makhmudov B. I. O. G. L. (2021). Influence of thermophysical properties of external barrier structures. Science and Education, 2(5), 182–192.